

IMPLEMENTATION OF CHILD-FRIENDLY EDUCATION THROUGH ISLAMIC EDUCATION AT SMPN 1 BOJONG, PURWAKARTA REGENCY

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Abstract

This study aims to describe: 1) the background of the implementation of child-friendly schools at SMPN 1 Bojong, 2) the implementation of child-friendly schools through Islamic Religious Education at SMPN 1 Bojong, and 3) the impact of the implementation of child-friendly schools through Islamic Religious Education at SMPN 1 Bojong. This research is a qualitative research, the subject consists of vice principals, PAI teachers, PKN teachers, and students. Data collection techniques are carried out by interviews, observation, and documentation. The results showed that: 1) the implementation of the child-friendly school program at SMPN 1 Bojong was motivated by the decision of the Purwakarta Regency government to make SMPN 1 Bojong a child-friendly school to answer parents' concerns about news of child violence at school. 2) The implementation of child-friendly schools at SMPN 1 Bojong focuses on the Islamic Religious Education program through five habituations, namely the habituation of greetings, the habituation of duha prayers, the habituation of Friday lectures, the habituation of memorization of juz 30, and the habituation of garbage greetings. 3) the impact of the implementation of child-friendly schools through Islamic Education at SMPN 1 Bojong, namely the formation of character, fun learning, and the active role of parents and the community to participate in implementing child-friendly education programs.

Keywords: School, Child Friendly, Islamic Religious Education, Implementation.

INTRODUCTION

One of the crimes that has been in the public spotlight lately is a case of violence against children. Children are the next generation of the nation who have a task in social development, so it is necessary to foster with affection, so that children are able to accept the responsibilities given in the future. (Santoso, 2023)

The next generation of the nation must have the ability to grow and develop to become mature individuals, physically and mentally healthy, have good education, have morals, and have good behavior. To achieve this goal, it requires full attention and guidance from the surrounding environment. Article 28B paragraph (2) of the 1945 Constitution states that every child has the right to survival, growth and development and the right to protection from violence and discrimination (Rosalin, 2020). Wrong treatment of children will affect the formation of the child's personality in the future. The quality of children will

decline if children's rights are not fulfilled, which will cause problems for the state, government, society, family, and parents.(Santoso, 2023)

Acts of violence against children can happen anywhere, even in places that we think are safe, such as schools. In fact, educational institutions can also be a place for violence, which has the potential to threaten children around them. The form of violence that arises in the school environment is not only limited to physical violence, but also in the form of psychological and sexual violence. Violence is committed by students against students, students to teachers, teachers to students, and parents to teachers.

Schools as a forum for the educational process must have a number of qualified educators, relevant curriculum, friendly culture, adequate facilities, and a safe and conducive environment for students in an effort to get an effective and holistic education. Education is a conscious and organized effort to create a learning environment that allows learners to develop themselves actively. The main objective of education is to assist learners in actualizing their potential, which includes spiritual aspects, self-control, personality development, intellectual development, good moral development, as well as mastery of various skills necessary both for themselves and for their contribution to society, state, and nation. This principle is regulated in Law No. 2 of 2003 concerning the National Education System.(Indonesian Child Protection Commission, 2006)

In an effort to protect children and to reduce acts of violence against children, especially in the world of education, the government makes a child protection policy in education units called Child Friendly Schools (SRA).

The Ministry of Women's Empowerment and Child Protection (PPPA) issued PPPA Regulation number 8 of 2014 concerning child-friendly school policies. According to PPPA Regulation Number 8 of 2014 Article 1 states that Child Friendly Schools are educational units, formal, non-formal, and informal that are safe, clean and healthy, caring and cultured environment, able to guarantee, fulfill, respect children's rights and protect children from violence, discrimination, and other mistreatment and support children's participation especially in planning, policy, learning, supervision and complaint mechanisms related to the fulfillment of children's rights and protection in education.(Santoso, 2023)

CFS must be able to ensure that education units are able to develop children's interests, talents and abilities and prepare children to be responsible for a tolerant, respectful, and cooperative life for progress and the spirit of peace.(Rosalin, 2020)

CFS was developed with the hope of fulfilling the rights and protecting one-third of children's lives (8 hours a day) while they are in the education unit. CFS is a paradigm shift to make adults in education units become parents and friends of students in their daily interactions in education units, so the commitment for education units to become CFS is a very important commitment in saving children's lives.(Rosalin, 2020)

Child-friendly schools build a new paradigm in educating and teaching students to create a resilient generation without violence, fostering the active role of teachers and other

school citizens to fulfill the rights and protect students. Child-friendly schools are needed to protect children's rights so that children feel comfortable when they are in school, and children's potential will be easy to develop and quality.

Based on data from community complaints to the Social Office of Women's Empowerment and Child Protection (PPPA) of Purwakarta Regency in 2020 until now, there have been 353 cases of violence, dominated by cases of violence and sexual abuse against children.

Creating a child-friendly school environment and learning atmosphere is an obligation for schools, especially teachers. The Purwakarta Regency Government is committed to developing Child Friendly Schools, in accordance with Purwakarta Regent Regulation Number 105 of 2019 concerning Child Friendly Schools.

SMPN 1 Bojong is one of the schools that has implemented the Child Friendly School Program effectively through Islamic Religious Education as a basic benchmark in tackling violence against children at school. Islamic religious education is needed because PAI is a source of self-fortification against the progress of the times in order to always obey Allah SWT, stay away from prohibitions and carry out His commands. Especially for school age who are unstable or are looking for self-identity, if it is not fortified with Islamic Religious Education, it is feared that it will fall into negative things. (Khoiruddin & Sholekah, 2019)

Based on this description, researchers are interested in researching how the implementation of child-friendly schools through Islamic Religious Education at SMPN 1 Bojong and what is behind the realization of child-friendly schools at SMPN 1 Bojong, and the impact of the implementation of child-friendly schools through Islamic Religious Education at SMPN 1 Bojong. With the title "Implementation of Child-Friendly Education through Islamic Education at SMPN 1 Bojong, Purwakarta Regency".

METHOD

This research is a type of qualitative research that aims to describe descriptively the implementation of the concept of Child Friendly Schools through Islamic religious education at State Junior High School 1 Bojong, Purwakarta, West Java.

The research subjects consisted of six resource persons divided into several groups, namely one vice principal, two Islamic Religious Education teachers, one Civic Education (PKN) teacher, and two students from State Junior High School 1 Bojong. They were chosen as research subjects because they have a relevant role in the context of implementing the Child Friendly School program through Islamic religious education in the school. The object of this study is the Islamic Religious Education program which is part of efforts to implement the concept of Child Friendly Schools at State Junior High School 1 Bojong. To collect data, this study uses several techniques, including observation, interviews, and documentation. Observation techniques are used to directly observe situations and activities that occur in schools in the context of implementing Child Friendly Schools. Interviews were conducted with resource persons to gain their views and experiences regarding the Islamic Religious Education program and the implementation of the Child Friendly School concept. Meanwhile, documentation is used

to collect existing data such as documents related to education programs and the concept of Child Friendly Schools. The purpose of collecting data through these various techniques is to ensure that the data obtained is representative and in-depth so that it can describe the phenomenon of implementing Child Friendly Schools through Islamic Religious Education at Sekolah Menengah Junior Negeri 1 Bojong comprehensively.

RESEARCH RESULTS

Background of the Implementation of Child Friendly Schools at SMPN 1 Bojong

Based on the results of interviews with vice principals and teachers at SMPN 1 Bojong, the background of the implementation of the child-friendly school program at SMPN 1 Bojong is because of parents' concerns about cases of violence against children that occur in schools, so the government is trying to reduce the number of violence against children through various means. One of them is the government making a child protection policy in education units called Child Friendly Schools (SRA). Child Friendly Schools (SRA) are formal, non-formal and informal education units that are able to provide fulfillment of special rights and protections for children including complaint mechanisms for handling cases in education units. (Rosalin, 2020)

In accordance with the decision of the Regent of Purwakarta Number 421 / Kep.430-DISDIK / 2019 concerning the Establishment of Child Friendly Schools in Purwakarta Regency, SMPN 1 Bojong is one of the schools directly appointed to be one of the school models that implement the Child Friendly School program. This is as stated in the interview: *"Child-friendly schools are government programs, and our schools that are SMP 1 are automatically designated as child-friendly school models."* (interview with Vice Principal, August 21, 2023).

Indeed, school should be the second environment after home for children to learn well and comfortably. In the interview the Vice Principal said that: *"If you look at it in general, schools are now required to be friendly schools. must be friendly to each other, friendly to their children, the environment must also be friendly, parents must also be friendly and vice versa, the workplace, the classroom environment must also be friendly."* (Vice Principal of SMPN 1 Bojong).

In its implementation, it is important to run in accordance with the established concept. As stated by the PAI teacher : *"In the agenda of the meeting, the principal said that child-friendly school programs must prioritize the approach to children more to invite than to command."* (PAI teacher of SMPN 1 Bojong).

Teachers are expected to be able to facilitate students in fulfilling their rights and protecting them from forms of violence. Therefore, it is very important to be committed to improving the morale and motivation of teachers in carrying out their duties as educators in order to create a child-friendly educational environment.

High teacher commitment makes them have a strong bond with students. In addition to teachers, the role of parents and the community is no less important. Parents must be

able to cooperate with the school in realizing a child-friendly school by setting a good example in their daily lives and comfort at home, because home is the first school for children. The community must also fully support by creating a good environment. With a strong commitment from three parties, the child-friendly school program will be realized easily.(Wati et al., 2021)

Implementation of Child Friendly Schools through PAI

In its implementation, SMPN 1 Bojong emphasizes the Child Friendly School program through Islamic education by carrying out various positive habits.

The first habituation begins with the habituation of greetings to form a polite and friendly personality. This habit is done by students when entering school in the morning, as stated in the interview: *"Every day the teacher is scheduled to arrive earlier than the student. When entering the school, the teachers were already lined up in front of the gate to habitually greet and welcome the students. This tradition is commonly called ngabaduy." (interview of PAI teacher of SMPN 1 Bojong).* In the process of greeting, male teachers and female students or vice versa should not touch because all students are required to have ablution from home to perform the second habituation, namely, praying sunnah duha. This is as the following interview suggests: *"When meeting teachers, children always shake hands and say hello. Except in the morning. Male teachers and female students or vice versa do not shake hands because children must have ablution to perform duha prayers before learning begins. Monday's exception is because of the flag ceremony." (interview of PAI teacher of SMPN 1 Bojong).*

In providing good education to children, PAI teachers work with all homeroom teachers to provide religious direction and guidance to equip students for community life later. Like the third habituation, namely Kultum or Friday lecture. *"Every Friday there is a cult program. All the officers from the students from the mc to the prayer closed. This is a provision to students if they are involved in the community." (interview of PAI teacher of SMPN 1 Bojong).* This cult aims to train students' mentality and abilities in society, as well as foster mutual respect and respect. As stated in the Vice Principal's interview, *"There are moments when children can appreciate others, for example when their friends are performers in Friday lectures, there is something that is instilled, namely learning to dare to appear and try to appreciate even though their performance is not optimal." (interview with the Vice Principal of SMPN 1 Bojong).*

The fourth habituation is the habituation of memorization of the Qur'an juz 30. This memorization is a recommendation to improve brain performance and this is a special program from PAI teachers. *"Juz 30 memorization is a program from PAI teachers, it is more of a recommendation. Although it is recommended, some are up to khatam." (teacher of PAI SMPN 1 Bojong).* For the implementation of the juz 30 memorization program in schools, PAI teachers need the role of parents, ustadz and community leaders to be able to take part in implementing the program in their respective homes. *"So far the program is running smoothly, because of the support of parents and the help of the ustadz in their respective homes in helping the children's memorization. Because we only accept*

memorized deposits, while the guidance is assisted by their respective bishops." (teacher of PAI SMPN 1 Bojong). This memorization has no specific time, aka unscheduled. Children usually take advantage of free time at school to deposit their memorization.

The fifth habituation is garbage greetings. Garbage greetings are activities for students to foster a love for cleanliness by picking up garbage around them and disposing of them in their place. As said in the interview : *"there is also a habit of garbage greetings that are done when the bell rings, children go out of class while picking up trash around and throwing it in the trash." (PKN teacher of SMPN1 Bojong).*

In the implementation of these five habituations, of course, it does not always run smoothly. As the PAI teacher said in the interview that: *"so far there have been no obstacles, it's just that there are still students who are lazy to follow the habituation. But teachers have also prevented such things by patrolling vulnerable places." All programs will not be able to be implemented if there is no good cooperation. Do not close your eyes, because there will definitely be some students who still violate. However, as a teacher who applies the principles of child-friendly schools, if anyone violates or makes a mistake, of course it does not provide corporal punishment, but is coaching in nature, such as being reprimanded, warned and directed by considering guiding and educational actions. "If anyone violates, we provide coaching. We talked to him and advised him. The next day it is watched whether it is still like that or not. There is no corporal punishment. If there is no change then we have to write istighfar 100x and that is already the most severe sanction." (teacher of PAI SMPN 1 Bojong).*

There are factors supporting the implementation of the child-friendly school program through Islamic Education at SMPN 1 Bojong, namely:

Trained and Competent Teachers

Trained and competent teachers greatly influence the development of children at school. Because basically a teacher is always an example for his students. *"At least every month there are always those who attend seminars or activities that mingle with other teachers in each region to share and find answers to problems and get new knowledge". (interview with the Vice Principal of SMPN 1 Bojong).*

SMPN 1 Bojong is committed to increasing the motivation and morale of teachers to realize Child Friendly Schools, namely by conducting socialization about child-friendly schools to raise awareness of the importance of the program, coaching how to communicate well with children so that children become more comfortable and open in learning, teachers always support the talents of students, teachers must try to be more creative and innovative in delivering learning, Evaluating the learning that has been carried out to be even better, teachers carry out positive habituation as a good example such as greeting friendly, inviting healthy living, and giving equal rights to all students.

Proper Facilities and Infrastructure

To succeed the program, physical improvements are also needed such as classrooms that are arranged to be more comfortable learning, there are toilets that are suitable for use, the availability of clean water, there are mosques and others.

Facilities and infrastructure in SMPN 1 Bojong consist of: classrooms, special / separate toilets, clean water, mosques and ablution places, the availability of drinking water depots / gallons, water taps in each front of the classroom, sports fields, stages, pavilions, mini soccer fields, and cooperatives. This facility is adequate to support the implementation of child-friendly school programs. *"With schools providing comfortable places maybe it's the idea of child-friendly schools, the rules are like that. It must be mutually friendly including the environment as well."* (Vice Principal of SMPN 1 Bojong).

The school provides facilities to support child-friendly school programs, so as to create a friendly environment, clean environment, and of course make students feel more comfortable and safe in school.

The Impact of Child-Friendly Education through Islamic Education

Child-friendly school programs through Islamic religious education have a significant impact in shaping individual views, values, and behavior. This can affect morals, ethics, and attitudes towards life.

Character Building

The application of habituation through Islamic religious education provides progress in the formation of good and religious character such as mutual respect, courtesy, friendliness, discipline, diligent worship and willingness to cooperate. This was conveyed in an interview with the vice principal: *"Because of frequent worship, the negative things that are usually done are reduced. And the child's mentality is more awake."* Religious education can motivate individuals to do good deeds and avoid acts that are prohibited in Islamic teachings.

By instilling the habituation of Islamic religious education, students also begin to have an awareness of the importance of doing good habits. This habituation program makes students more diligent and disciplined. *"Just by hearing the ringing of the bell, the children understood that they were required to gather immediately."* (PAI teacher interview).

Discipline will have a good influence on the lives of students. Children who are usually disciplined will continue to apply it to what they do and it has a good impact on their lives in the future.

Fun Learning

The habituation carried out by SMPN 1 Bojong received direct guidance and direction from the teachers. When students make mistakes, there is no corporal punishment, only coaching and advice, then directed again. This of course makes students feel happy because of the comfort provided by the teachers. *"The teacher here sets a good example in habituation and is always friendly, it's also cool to be invited to chat. So we are not*

awkward." (MY, student of SMPN 1 Bojong). Comfort makes children feel more at home in school and feel given their rights as a learner.

The Role of Parents and Community Leaders

Good cooperation will realize our goals easily. As happened at SMPN 1 Bojong between PAI teachers, parents and ustadz in implementing child-friendly schools through Islamic religious education. *"We work with parents and bishops who are in their homes. For example, when children don't pay their salaries, they call us to tell them. And vice versa."* (interview of PAI teacher of SMPN 1 Bojong).

The role of parents and community leaders is very much needed. Because without doing a good role, this program is just planning.

DISCUSSION

From the data analysis that has been done, there are important findings in this study, namely: first, the background of the implementation of the child-friendly school program at SMPN 1 Bojong is because of the government's program to respond to parents' concerns about child violence in the school environment, SMPN 1 Bojong was appointed directly to be one of the models of child-friendly schools in Purwakarta Regency.

This finding is in accordance with the Child Friendly School Guidelines that in order to form a child-friendly school, there are several stages carried out consisting of the formation stage and the development stage. At the formation stage we call it by the term "MAU". As a form of commitment and synergy, all stages of CFS formation and development are carried out by local governments and education units. One of them is a request to the education unit to "MAU" become CFS in two ways, namely Top Down and Bottom Up. The stages of forming CFS at SMPN 1 Bojong use the Top Down method, which means, the local government or related regional apparatus invites or asks education units in their areas to become CFS. All education units that "MAU" will be made SRA Decrees determined by the Regional Head / Head of the Education Office / Regional Office / Kanwil / Religious Office / PPPA Office.(Rosalin, 2020) The government hopes that the Child-Friendly School program can help overcome violence against children in the educational environment. Because it is very unfortunate that in reality there are so many terrible incidents that can tarnish the good image of the world of education, such as cases of violence against children committed by teachers, fights between students, sexual abuse of children and others. In Article 54 paragraph (1) of Law Number 32 of 2014 concerning Amendments to Law Number 23 of 2002 concerning Child Protection, which states that "Children in and within the education unit must receive protection from physical, psychological, sexual crimes, and other crimes committed by educators, education staff, fellow students, and/or other parties."(Rosalin, 2020)

Second, SMPN 1 Bojong uses habituation methods in realizing the Child-Friendly School Program through Islamic Religious Education. Habituation is something that is deliberately done repeatedly so that something can become a habit. This method of habituation is based on experience, because what is habituated is something that is

practiced. The essence of habit is repetition. Habituation places man as something special, which can save strength, because it will become an inherent and spontaneous habit, so that the activity can be carried out in every job. Therefore, this method is very effective in order to foster the character and personality of the child.(Ahsanulhaq, 2019)

There are several habituations carried out, namely through the habituation of greetings, duha prayers, Friday lectures, memorization and garbage greetings. The habituation of greetings can create more positive and harmonious relationships between learners, create a friendly environment and support better social interaction. The habit of praying duha increases blessings and spirituality in everyday life, because through this practice students consistently get closer to God by doing additional worship at the beginning of the morning. Through Friday lectures learners gain religious knowledge and spiritual advice. In addition, learners are trained in courage to form a strong mentality. Next is the habituation of memorization of juz 30. Although only a recommendation, it is proven that students are very ambitious to complete their memorization until khatam. Through memorization, students can practice their ability to remember and focus, especially their age which is very supportive of fast memorization entry. The last habituation is garbage greetings. This habituation aims to create a love for cleanliness. Because cleanliness is partly based on faith. By applying garbage greetings, students have a sense of care and responsibility for the surrounding environment. Because a clean environment will create a comfortable and beautiful atmosphere of course.

The five habituations certainly contain worship values that make students aware of the purpose of life in the world, lead to positive actions, be more responsible, and deepen the relationship with God. This research is relevant to previous research which states that in the world of education, Islamic religious education is needed because PAI is a source of self-fortification against the progress of the times in order to always obey Allah SWT, stay away from prohibitions and carry out His commands. Especially for school age who are unstable or are looking for self-identity, if it is not fortified with Islamic Religious Education, it is feared that it will fall into negative things.(Khoiruddin & Sholekah, 2019)

This habituation program will not be realized without supporting factors. Competent teachers and proper infrastructure are one of the supporting factors for the realization of child-friendly education implementation. Therefore, in its implementation, it is important to run in accordance with the concept of child-friendly schools that have been set. There are 4 concepts of child-friendly schools, namely: (1) changing the paradigm from teachers to guides, parents and friends of children. (2) Parents set an example in daily life. (3) Ensure that adults in schools are fully involved in protecting children. (4) Ensure parents and children are actively involved in fulfilling the 6 components of CFS(Rosalin, 2020). Aspects of adequate infrastructure, especially those related to the learning needs of students. The infrastructure does not have to be expensive but according to the needs of the child. The existence of safe and safe zones to schools, the existence of cigarette-free areas, inclusive education are also factors that schools pay attention to. Arrangement of school and classroom environments that are attractive, attractive, impressive, parenting,

and individual approaches so that the school becomes a comfortable and pleasant place (Indonesian Child Protection Commission, 2006).

Third, the implementation of Child-Friendly Schools through Islamic Education at SMPN 1 Bojong has an impact on character building, fun learning, and the active role of parents and the community in supporting school programs. Through religious habituation, it can provide progress in the formation of good and religious children's character and have the ability to socialize as a provision of life in society. This research is relevant to previous research, Imam Ghazali explained that the formation of religious character can be done through strategies or habit-forming methods. This method is the formation of good habits and abandonment of bad habits through guidance, training, and hard work. The formation of this habit will be a person's character a person's character, then a strong character is usually formed by the value of cultivation that emphasizes good and bad. (Khoiruddin & Sholekah, 2019) Comfortable learning is created because of comfort. Comfort itself can come from teachers, friends, and a safe environment. This finding is relevant to previous findings stating that students who experience good treatment in school are happier. Child-friendly schools make students feel comfortable and happy to be in school, this has implications for increasing academic success and students' social skills (Wati et al., 2021). This religious habituation program causes parents and the community to be involved in it with their respective roles. When at home, parents should model good behavior to be a model that their children can emulate. The community can participate starting with providing financial assistance, building construction, local, fencing, and so on. The public can also be involved in the technical field of education; Educational technical assistance is also very likely to be provided, such as: providing themselves as teachers, helping children with reading difficulties, determining and maintaining new qualified teachers, and discussing curriculum implementation and learning progress. (Indonesian Child Protection Commission, 2006)

CONCLUSION

Based on the results of the study, it is known that the background of the implementation of the child-friendly school program at SMPN 1 Bojong is due to the Decree of the Regent of Purwakarta concerning the Establishment of Child-Friendly Schools in Purwakarta Regency and SMPN 1 Bojong was appointed to be one of the models of child-friendly schools. then in its implementation, SMPN 1 Bojong focuses on the Islamic education program, namely habituation that contains worship values. These habits are the habituation of greetings, the habituation of duha prayers, the habituation of Friday lectures, the habituation of memorization, and the habituation of garbage greetings. The impact of child-friendly schools through Islamic religious education at SMPN 1 Bojong can be seen from the formation of children's character, students feel happy and comfortable during the learning process, and the active role of parents and the community to participate in implementing it.

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